

The Evolution of Accounting Measurement: Issues and Prospects

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Abstract

This study focuses on the advancement of accounting measurement from historical costs to the contemporary times of fair value reporting. The study looked at both measures, identifying their strengths and challenges. From the views of notable scholars on the subject matter, it has been revealed that although the need of investors for decision useful information has advanced the use of fair value accounting (FVA) measurement being that it derives from current market prices, historical cost accounting (HCA) remains useful in current times due to its objectivity in the measurement of transactions and events. From prior researches, it has been demonstrated that the furtherance of accounting measurement continues. The study concluded by suggesting the way forward despite the dilemma that exist between both measurements by establishing a mixed model that will capture the good qualities of both measurements.

Keywords: Accounting measurement, Fair Value Accounting, Historical cost Accounting

JEL Classification: M40, N01

1. Introduction

From history, accounting effort at measurement of economic events is transitioning. Once, the traditional historical cost approach held sway. Prior to Historical Cost Accounting (HCA), there was permissive valuation where management had the liberty to choose measurement models and assumptions that suited their interest (Amaefule et al., 2018). But the Stock market collapse of 1929 leading to the Great Depression changed the narratives. Then, HCA was birthed to subsequently prevent the overvaluation of assets believed to be responsible for the amplification of the Great Depression (Zyla, 2010). The accounting profession was hinged on Historical Cost Accounting (HCA) principle which posits that transactions and events should be recorded at their original transaction price (cost). Nevertheless, the increasing complexity of financial markets and global economic volatility since late 20th century prompted a "quiet revolution" (Dean et al., 2025).

By the 1970s, decision usefulness became a buzz over stewardship, as the primary objective of financial statements (Cordery & Sinclair, 2017). Investors' information need shifted from a

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record of what was spent (stewardship) to what an entity was worth now to make better decisions. In view of the limitations of HCA as it concerns the hyper-inflation of the 1970s and the emergence of derivatives and complex securities; HCA could not measure up to the realities of the market. Then the FASB (Financial Accounting Standards Board) in the United States of America (USA) and the IASB (International Accounting Standards Board) globally began introducing standards like SFAS 157 (now ASC 820) and IFRS 13, which formally defined Fair Value as an "exit price" (FASB, 2011).

HCA stands for objectivity and verifiability. This is because a historical transaction is backed by a physical receipt, contract or some other forms of evidence, it leaves little room for managerial manipulation (Watts, 2003). Moreover, HCA helps organisations to identify the outcome of the organization in financial terms because it generates information about the actual expenses and revenues of organisations. Despite the benefits of the HCA, Tkachuk (2019) is of the opinion that the HCA has limitations that range from irrelevance due to time factor and the crisis of subjectivity that characterized the HCA. Therefore, an urgent switch of paradigm became imperative because of progress in technology, increased complexity and dynamism of economic environments, and the investors' need for faster and relevant financial information for decision making purposes. The fair value approach was propounded to address the observed shortcoming of HCA perspective and to keep accounting values relevant and in line with changing economic and business realities.

The objective of this paper therefore is to examine the evolution of accounting measurement from Historical Cost Accounting to Fair Value Accounting with a view to highlight the challenges and prospects of both measurement as well as suggest the way forward towards accounting measurements.

The remaining part of this paper is divided into the following sections. Section two deals with the concept of historical cost accounting, section three is on addressing the dilemma between historical cost accounting and fair value accounting, section four is on the way forward while section five is conclusion.

2. The concept of Historical Cost Accounting

In the history of accounting measurement there have been oppositions stewardship and decision-usefulness as to which is the primary objective of financial information. Earlier accounting thought and theories favoured the stewardship objective, which emphasizes the accountant's role in reporting on management's use of resources (Edwards & Boyns, 2022). The Historical Cost Accounting (HCA), is a model where assets are recorded at their original transaction price dominated the measurement territory then, being in tandem with conservatism principle of accounting (Fontes et al., 2024).

However, Watts (2003), in his work titled "Conservatism in Accounting Part 1" argues that the shift toward fair value accounting (FVA) by the FASB would likely decrease accounting conservatism, making earnings less timely in reflecting bad news compared to good news, and increasing managerial discretion, particularly with the introduction of FVA in goodwill accounting (SFAS 142) and suggested that while FVA aims for greater relevance, its reliance on subjective estimates, especially for items like goodwill, creates opportunities for opportunistic management as well as reduces earnings quality. This condition is considered to be against the foundation of HCA which lies in conservatism and verifiability. HCA approach ensures that financial statements are free from managerial bias, as every figure is anchored to a past, verifiable exchange. HCA aligns with the principle of conservatism where assets and transactions are valued and recorded at their original cost at the time of event. However, this approach has been criticized for not reflecting current economic realities thereby incapable of

reflecting true worth of assets. This view by Watts (2003) seems to be contrary with an earlier study conducted by Barth et.al, (1995). In their study, Barth et.al. (1995) investigated the effect of fair value accounting on banks and came up with three findings. Firstly, fair value-based earnings are more volatile than historical cost earnings, though the observed difference in volatility does not impact share prices. Secondly, fair value-based violations enabled predictions of regulatory capital violations. However, share prices also do not mirror this potential increased regulatory risk but historical cost violations provided such market information. Finally, interest rates changes were mirrored on share prices, even within static investment securities' contractual cash flows. Historical Cost Accounting like many other concepts has its limitations which became the reason for the appearing of fair value accounting.

2.1 Limitations of the Historical Cost Accounting

Literature (li, 2025; Oyewo, 2020; Qiu, 2025) highlights two critical environmental and economic prompts that dwindled the dominance of HCA and created opportunity for Fair Value Accounting (FVA):

2.1.1 Inflation and Economic Volatility

Research by Barlev and Haddad (2003) identified that during the high-inflation era of the 1970s, HCA became increasingly irrelevant because HCA does not account for changes in the purchasing power of money or the replacement cost of assets. Therefore, balance sheets significantly understated the true economic value of firms. This created a demand for current value models that could reflect the impact of inflation on a company's capital maintenance (Mathews & Perera, 1996).

2.1.2 Financial Derivatives and Complex Instruments

The rise of the global financial sector introduced liquid assets that HCA was incapable handling. For example, financial derivatives and complex securities frequently possess zero historical cost or near-zero but still have huge market value and significant risk. However, with the development of standards like SFAS 157 and IFRS 13-Fair Value Measurement, there now exist a way to logically and transparently value these rather volatile assets Ariany, 2024; Fontes et al., 2024; McDonough et al., 2020)

2.1.3 Issue of Relevance and Reliability

Many researchers ((McDonough et al., 2020; O'Connell et al., 2020) observed that there is always an exchange between relevance and reliability with regards to accounting measurement approaches (i.e. HCA and FVA). While some scholars such as Barth et al. (2001) and Landsman (2007) favoured FVA for its relevance, others such as Ronen (2008) and Rayman (2007) support HCA for its reliability.

2.2 Fair Value Accounting

FVA is defined by the Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB) as “the price that would be received to sell an asset or paid to transfer a liability” (FASB, 1991). Fair value accounting has been promoted as being able to provide a better, more comprehensive, and consistent framework for financial reporting that would ensure relevance, enhance comparability, and timely reflection of up-to-date market prices and current economic realities (Barth, 2006). Although, this position has been countered by scholars (Kanodia & Sapra, 2016) pointing to the subjectivity, complexity, and susceptibility of FVA to manipulation by management.

Fair value accounting has significant implications for financial reporting, affecting asset valuation, income recognition, and financial statement volatility (KPMG, 2017). Laux and Leuz, (2010) carried out a study to ascertain whether FVA contributed to or amplified the 2008 financial crisis. In their findings, they argued that it is improbable that fair-value accounting contributed to the severity of the 2008 financial crisis in a significant manner noting that there

may have been downward spirals or asset-fire sales in certain markets, but there is no evidence to claim that they are a result of fair-value accounting. Also, they found no clear support for the assertion that fair-value accounting caused excessive write-downs of banks' assets rather empirical evidence was said to point in the opposite direction which is overvaluation of bank assets.

Lefebvre et al. (2009) took a study on fair value accounting and states that while stating that Fair value convention has polarized two opposing views – the first, that fair value accounting compounds economic hardship and distortion – and the second, that fair value accounting affords an accurate rendering of the market value of underlying assets and liabilities, analysis shows that only certain assets and liabilities are required to be measured at fair value and the degree to which unrealized gains and losses associated with fair value measurement are reflected in the financial statements depends on the intended use of assets and liabilities in question.

Again, Penman (2012) evaluated whether fair value is a plus or a minus. His study reveals that the issue of when, rather than how, fair value measurement should be applied is still far from resolved, However, Fair values have been mandated for some assets and liabilities under both IASB and FASB standards, but it is fair to say that principles governing the applicability of fair values have yet to be articulated”

Bernet and Hladika (2025) conducted a study titled “The Evolution of Fair Value Accounting: A Bibliometric and Historical Analysis of Scientific Perspectives” using a combination of bibliometric and content analysis as methodology. The study reveals that Interest in fair value accounting increased significantly as a result of the 2008 financial crisis. However, the study also raises concern on the issues of reliability, relevance, volatility, and decision-usefulness of information provided. They again observe that there is a recent shift in the literature toward linking fair value accounting with broader themes such as sustainability and corporate social responsibility

Fair value accounting (FVA) has also attracted regulatory attention, with concerns about its impact on financial stability and procyclicality (SEC, 2008). Some researchers (Laux & Leuz, 2010) argued that fair value accounting can exacerbate financial crises, while others contend that it provides valuable information for investors (Barth, 2006).

2.2.1 The Pro-Fair Value View vs. the Pro-Historical Cost View

Barth et al. (2001) and Landsman (2007) are adherents of the fair value view and maintain that FVA is fundamentally better at relevance. They contended that historical cost approach provides obviously little or no information about the future. Therefore, they support fair value measurements have elevated relevance in value determination, being more associated with the stock market prices of the firms concerned.

On the other hand, some champions of the Historical Cost view which include Ronen (2008) and Rayman (2007) opined that FVA determined values are innately unreliable. This is most especially where there no active markets. They argue that FVA is grossly subjective and susceptible managerial manipulation. Investors who depend on these valuations may end up being misled. Conversely, HCA is considered objective.

Barth and Landsman (1995) are among the promoters of FVA who claim that FVA is suitable in perfect market conditions because it is a true reflection of all available information. This view aligns with the Efficient Market Hypothesis (strong Form). On the flip side, the opposition like Ronen (2008) declare otherwise noting that FVA creates unreal fluctuations in values due

to its subjectiveness and proneness to managerial manipulations especially in the absence active markets.

In the review of the alleged contribution of FVA in the 2008 Global Financial Crisis, Laux and Leuz (2010) posit that even when there is indication that FVA amplified the crisis, there was no evidence of such volatility affecting the stock prices of banks. Still, Critics like Plantin and Sapra (2008) argue that FVA creates procyclicality (a feedback loop where falling market prices force banks to write down assets). Yet again, studies by the SEC (2008) and academic reviews especially Liao et al. (2021) concluded that FVA was likely the emissary rather than the source of the crisis, simply showcase the intrinsic economic reality that HCA would otherwise not disclose.

The evolution from HCA to FVA has been one of theoretical debate revolving mainly around relevance and reliability which has presented a fundamental trade-off in accounting thought. Summarily, the differences between the HCA and the FVA are stated in the table 1

Table 1: Differences between Historical Cost Measurement and Fair Value Measurement

Feature	Historical Cost	Fair Value
Strength	Reliability and Verifiability (Ronen, 2008; Tkachuk, 2019)	Relevance and Timeliness (Bernet & Hladika, 2025; Watts, 2003; Landsman, 2007)
Focus	Past Transactions (Rayman, 2007; Tamplin, 2023)	Current Market Expectations (Lefebvre et al., 2009)
Level of Variability	Low volatility (Tkachuk, 2019)	High Market fluctuations (Barth et al., 1995; Ronen, 2008)
Approach	Backward-looking and Static (Bernet & Hladika, 2025)	Forward-looking and Dynamic (Liao et al., 2021; Mehta, 2025)

Source: compiled by author (2025)

2.2.2 Challenges of Fair Value Accounting

Despite the support for fair value accounting, it has been asserted that it is not without limitations. Scholars such as O'Connell et al. (2020), Miciuła et al. (2020), Oyewo (2020), Fontes et al. (2024) and Mehta (2025) have stated some of the various challenges associated with the FVA. These challenges are briefly discussed.

Subjective and involves Managerial Judgment: This leads to lack of certainty, results in loss of comparability and provides opportunity for manipulations.

Complex Measure: Arising from the above, using FVA involve making complex estimates.

The quality of Procyclicality: FVA may amplify or dampen economic realities resulting in unreal volatility.

Opportunity for Creative Accounting: Due to its flexibility, FVA can encourage managers to engineer financial results to be reported.

Uncertainty in measurement of Value: Less active markets or economic volatility increase uncertainty, making reliable valuation difficult.

Comparability issues: The liberty to use different approaches and assumptions by different organizations or at different periods within same entity hampers the comparability of financial statements.

Existence of Imperfect market: Perfect markets hardly exist. Under imperfect markets, companies have the leverage to resort to internal, highly subjective techniques.

Auditing Difficulties: Audit risk- the risk that financial statement may contain material errors and misstatement that cannot be detected by audit procedure- will be very high when subjective fair value estimates are used in valuation.

The implication of these challenges is that FVA is far from completely replacing HCA. The current development is one geared towards organizations adopting a hybrid valuation model solution in financial reporting. FVA is usually applied for liquid financial instruments listed under IFRS 13 because of its capacity to produce timely, relevant current market values. But HCA maintains prominence for non-financial assets owing to its excellence in reliability and objectivity.

3. HCA vs FVA: Addressing the Dilemma

Significant progress has been made over the years in addressing the dilemma associated with transiting from Historical Cost Accounting to Fair Value Accounting. Currently, the successes recorded are underscored below as identified by scholars such as Kanodia and Sapra (2016), Miciuła et al. (2020), and Qiu (2025).

Financial Sector adoption: FVA is largely used for the valuation of highly liquid financial instruments to the level that it may have completely displaced HCA.

IFRS Support: IFRS under IAS 16 has recommended that after the initial recognition using HCA, property, plant, and equipment (PPE) and intangibles should periodically be revalued to their fair value. Although there is a divergence with US GAAP on this matter. In the US PPE is strictly valued using historical cost approach only.

Acceptance of the Hybrid Approach: The current trend favours the use of a blended approach. It is now acceptable to value some assets according to their nature and specific features using FVA while others are valued under HCA.

Creation of Exception: An exception to IAS 16 mentioned above has also been made by IFRS regarding investment property. Companies can value their investment property using FVA instead of HCA.

4. The way forward

Despite the efforts made by regulatory bodies in addressing the dilemma between HCA and FVA, the issues of reliability and relevance, subjectivity and volatility, financial and non-financial instruments still abound. While efforts are being made to ensure accuracy in financial reporting by adopting appropriate measurement, it is worthy to note that in this era of digitalization and artificial intelligence pose a threat to the traditional methods of measurement. Based on the aforementioned, it is therefore necessary to make the following suggestions

1. The development of a mixed model framework that will adopt the good qualities of both measurements is necessary to avoid any dilemma that may arise from time to time.
2. New digital assets should be integrated into measurement systems

3. There should be clear guidance on fair value estimation to avert the flaws of subjectivity in measurement

5. Conclusion

In response to the dynamic need of a constantly changing global economic and business environment, accounting measurement is still transitioning from HCA to FVA. FVA cannot be said to have invalidated or completely replaced HCA. Both approaches are still useful today based on the evaluation of their respective strengths and weaknesses. The coexistence of both approaches has often resulted in the use a hybrid solution i.e. a parallel application of both approaches to different classes of transaction and assets in the same financial statements. While HCA is rated to reliable, stable and verifiable, FVA adapts to the fluidity of the market, providing relevant, timely financial information. The future of accounting thought as regards the concept of Value, likely lies in a compromise between HCA and FVA where some assets will continue to be measured at cost while others especially liquid financial assets will report at their fair market value.

Literature suggests that neither HCA nor FVA is an elixir on the issue of measurement. Therefore, current accounting thought is gravitating toward the Mixed-Attribute Model, where different measurement approaches are used based on the distinct features of the assets and the obtainability of market data.

As accounting standards continue to evolve, it is clearly important for practitioners, managers, investors and other stakeholders to understand impact of using either of HCA and FVA for decision-making and for reporting financial results.

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